

Technological Aspirations and Warnings in Classic Science Fiction of Verne and Wells

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Abstract

This research paper examines how Jules Verne and H.G. Wells, two very important science fiction writers, used their stories to explore how society remembers its past and imagines its future. Verne wrote during a time when technology was rapidly advancing. He was generally optimistic about what humans could achieve. His works, like "Twenty Thousand Leagues Under the Sea," celebrated human ingenuity and the spirit of exploration. He showed how science could improve lives and expand horizons. All of His characters often showed the excitement and pride people felt about new inventions. He also revealed that even with incredible inventions, ethical questions still exist. He warned that focusing only on technology could lose essential parts of who we are as people. Verne showed the good side of progress, while Wells highlighted the potential dangers. Both have used their stories to make people think about how technology affects society and how we remember our past. Verne's stories make us think about how to use technology to improve the world. Wells's stories warn us to be careful and thoughtful about how we use technology. Their books remind us that technology is robust and that we must use it wisely. They show how stories can help us understand our past and think about our future. Their work is still relevant today as we face new challenges with artificial intelligence and climate change. They show that we must remember our culture while we move forward with new inventions. They both show that literature is a way to keep cultural memory alive.

Keywords: Technology, Optimistic, Society, Cultural Memory, Potential dangers

Introduction

Literature is the mirror of society, and cultural memory is a big part of society. Cultural memory plays an essential role in literature, especially in science fiction. Science fiction literature is one of the best ways to understand cultural memory through literature. Science fiction authors bring culture into the literature to set new and imaginative contexts.

Verne and Wells explore progress and human advancement through technology. Verne often presents science positively, as it can improve human life. On the other hand, Wells was not exactly opposed to progress; he was afraid of a rapidly changing society and worried about the uncontrolled growth of technology, so he was unhappy with this progress. He warns of the social inequalities, ethical dilemmas, and the risk of unchecked technology. Both works reflect on their time's historical and cultural context, discussing imperialism, colonialism, and societal issues. They use fiction through imagination to efficiently engage the social problems, such as class division, which offers entertainment and critical social commentary. Their works are not only for fun and entertainment but also as cultural commentary, shaping and reflecting on collecting memories about science, society, and human progress.

The collective memory tradition shapes the future and conveys cultural memory in science fiction literature. Verne and Wells understand the past and present and imagine the future. In their narratives, they both tried to improve human life through science and technology; they incorporate the history and identity themes when the writer imagines the future, and they think about the past and present historical events and traditions, especially in science fiction literature's unique way to know the cultural memory, because authors create an alternative reality.

The works of Jules Verne and H.G. Wells have profoundly impacted contemporary thought, shaping the development of science fiction as a genre and influencing broader cultural and philosophical discourses. Their imaginative narratives challenge readers to consider the ethical dimensions of scientific progress and the potential results of technological change. By engaging with these themes, Verne and Wells continue to inspire critical reflection and creative exploration, leaving a lasting legacy that transcends the boundaries of time and space.

The research methodologies employed in this study include qualitative analysis, focusing on thematic and narrative techniques within primary texts by

The Role of Technology in Verne's Cultural Memory

Jules Verne is the father of science fiction, writing around 80 books; most books are about adventure and science. His works related to anxiety and the cultural desire of the 19th century. Verne applied technology to society and tried to improve human life. In one of his famous works, "Twenty Thousand Leagues Under the Sea", he shows society's anxiety in that period. In his stories, we can see how technology improves society, and themes connect to cultural memory. In the 19th century, there were technological improvements during the Industrial Revolution; human life was improving, and the impact was on society and the economy. Some discoveries of the 19th century are easy to make human life, like the steam engine and telegraph; they can connect people from far away. Moreover, all we can see is the possibility of the future in Verne's narratives. Verne has shown us that technology can improve human life and how it can be destructive; through his narratives, he has warned society of this transformation. From 20000 Leagues Under the Sea, the submarine Nautilus not only represents the quality and human creativity in scientific development, but it was also a dream of the 19th century about how technology can change life and bring us to an ideal place. He was also conscious of the destructive sites. As we can see, it was tough to develop the submarine because Captain Nemo was the only one not in touch with society. His works pushed the readers to think about human capabilities, so his stories were not about scientific progress. Nautilus represents the limitless power of human rusticity. We can go to an unknown place and discover something new, showing a better future.

In "From the Earth to the Moon," he shows technological advancement in this story. It was a story about a club that wanted to reach the moon, and although it was impossible in his time, Verne made it possible. This projectile was not only the means of transport to reach the moon. It also represents Verne's imagination; readers can readily imagine going to the moon through Verne's narratives. Verne's characters were very ambitious. They were curious about exploring the moon. Technology can unite people and sometimes divide them; in Verne's narratives, the people unite because they have a dream of the moon. In this story, the projectile has two sides: one is hope, and the other is risk. However, people do not give risk importance here because the story focuses on fulfilling the dream. Today, we have to think about this project's positive and negative sides and take a huge responsibility; there can be a problem with using this unchecked technology. These are the cultural memories that Verne's works give us.

In Verne's other masterpiece, 'Around the World in Eighty Days,' he represents the train as a symbol, showing that technology can change human life and the idea that men can go around the world. The train was an innovative representation that was impossible, and it makes it possible in his narratives. Two discoveries from this story, the train and the steamship, are tools Fogg has used to complete his ambitious journey. This story shows how technology can change the human lifestyle, and in only 80 days, anyone can travel around the globe. This is an example of human potentiality; technology can increase human power. In this story, technology reduces geographical distance and creates relationships between countries and cultures. The protagonist, Philius Fogg, journey, meets many people from different countries and learns about their cultures. This meeting with other people was not only a positive side; there was a chance for misunderstanding and conflict. Also, it can remind us that it is not easy to form a good relationship. There is no difference between Verne's journey and today's times. The train was the fastest transport in his time, and today, the plane is the quickest, but both forms of transport have reduced the world, and we can quickly go anywhere.

Jules Verne talks about adventure and pushes us to think about how technology can change our identity. We can observe that His characters used new technology and always faced new challenges, and ultimately, they changed their identity through this process; they are not like before. It is connected with modern days; we can see how technology is changing our lives and how we discover ourselves. Verne was showing it in the 19th century. For example, Captain Nemo created an unknown world underwater for himself. He was the king of the Submarine here; we can see that technology has changed the king's identity. He was mysterious, and nobody knew about his past life; he was no longer an ordinary man. Technology has played an essential role in his transformation.

The Role of Technology in Wells's Cultural Memory

One of the greatest authors of science fiction is Herbert George Wells. In addition to providing pleasure, he made us consider how society is affected by the use of science and technology. This scientific advancement has the potential to enhance human existence. However, it might be detrimental to our identities and culture. He frequently depicts utopian and dystopian themes in his works. This part will go over scientific and technical developments through Verne's stories. He thinks this technological development may have positive and negative effects, primarily on cultural and traditional values. The likelihood of culture vanishing due to technical improvements is considerable.

.In Wells's works, science and technological development are the main reasons for transformation. This development increases human potential, grows knowledge, and expands society. According to Wells, it also has a darker side; he has shown one society where there will be a significant change. For example, in his story "The Time Machine," he showed time through travel. This novel is about the journey and could also birth profound discussion on memory and existence.

Wells showed a picture of people divided into two parts: Eloi and Morlocks. Eloi led an aristocratic life but slowly forgot about culture and tradition. On the other side, Morlocks stay underground, and they have become a slave to technology; this story highlights the darker side: technology controls humans and can destroy our culture and humanity. This division is based on the class division and technology broad this division. Morlocks are lower cast and come lower because of technology. On the other hand, Eloi is the higher cast. They profit from the benefits of technology, so the cast also plays a role in divisions besides technology.

In this novel, Wells not only shows the future and the class division; he uses this division to ask questions about whether humanity is fundamentally progressing or regressing. He makes us wonder if our focus on advancement might lead us to dependence and ignorance. Contemporary society reflects Wells's futurism; it pushes us to see how technological advancement influences memories.

Our culture and traditions play a significant role in shaping our identity. In the novel "The Time Machine," Eloi forget their past and lose their ambition and identity. Wells illustrates how culture and tradition help us understand our identity better. We can forget who we are and lose our sense of purpose if we lose our culture and traditions. Wells criticizes technological advances and says there is a chance to forget our culture and tradition because of technological advancements. He has indicated that in the contemporary world, where there is plenty of information, we must choose which ones are important.

How Technology shapes culture: a comparative study of Verne and Wells

Jules Verne and H.G. Wells are the pioneers of science fiction literature because they have made a massive contribution to this genre in their works. They force us to think beyond the stories, and these stories show us how cultural memory works. We can easily understand that Cultural memory changes us and helps us to rethink. We can learn about the cultural and social settings and how they interact with each other in their works. Verne's exploration made the national pride. In his stories, like 20000 leagues under the sea, Around the world in eighty days, and from the earth to the moon, he has shown the technological advancement and the potential of humans in the 19th century. In his works, technology is like a mirror in the cultural memory of the 19th century, reflecting the optimism and pessimism connected with scientific development. On the other hand, H.G. Wells criticizes society for the consequences of using unchecked technology. In his works, such as The War of the Worlds and The Invisible Man, he shows that technology can be cautious of society, and readers rethink it in their cultural memory. Wells shows imperialism, class barriers, and technological advancements through the cultural narratives in his works.

Both of the authors use technology as a double-edged sword. Verne used it for the new invention and used them to solve the problems and reach both as a personal and shared goal. For example, in "Around the World in Eighty Days," where he shows the principal character Phileas Fogg, who has completed his journey in the given time, throughout his journey, he explores the transportation medium like steamships and railways, and the technology helps the adventure and possible discovery. But on the other hand, Wells' characters often face problems because of technology. In The Time Machine, Eloi and Morlocks represent the division of society; Wells suggests that this inequality is a reflection of technology. Using technology was very exciting, but later it got out of control. This technology led to a deep crisis in the Victorian age, showing how people were worried.

By analyzing their works, we understand that their views on technological progress reflect the social attitude of their time. Verne portrayed a hopeful picture of technology, to achieve great things and explore the unknown territories. In contrast, Wells takes a more cautious stance; he often warns readers about the new, unchecked technology. This difference is not only for making the story enjoyable but also influences the readers to understand the role of technology in society.

Conclusion

Verne and Wells's cultural memories show different points of view, different methods, and different themes; both have shown different times. They interact in various ways in a cultural memory. Their stories are delightful, and through this interment, they have shown the way to improve society and, at the same

time, warned against destroying humanity. In Verne's narratives, we can see the complicated relationship between society's development and technology; this technology can take society ahead, but on the other hand, it can also face a big problem. In this story, science is fundamental, but determination and help from people are more important than science. In Wells's works, we are moving so fast toward technological advancement that we forget about culture, tradition, and humanity. He has warned us that we will live a hollow existence if we forget our past education. It looks like a mirror in Wells's imaginary world where we can see our shadow of the future. His works force us to think: Do we understand the darker side of technology? Second, are we forgetting the past while focusing solely on the future? We might gain a better understanding of ourselves by finding these questions.

Verne and Wells not only show cultural memory in different ways, but they also show the societal issues of their times. Verne focused on the imperialist themes of the 19th century; on the contrary, Wells had social transformation through science and technology in the early 20th century. These writers have shaped the literary forms through their narratives and connected their problems to the use of cultural memory. As a cultural memory, people can convey a generation to other generations and keep past events, ideas, and thinking in mind. They have mentioned societal problems that people are always thinking about. Verne and Wells both have different times; Most of Verne's works introduce us to a new place because Verne's time was the 19th century, when European countries captured other countries to expand their empires. Wells talked about the early 20th century when technology was changing quickly, society was transforming, and people had fear and anxiety. Verne and Wells proved that literature was not only for retirement; it was the mirror of society. We can easily understand that Verne and Wells wrote stories that informed the societal situation and the thinking of 19th and 20th-century people. Societal stories and identities are significant for cultural memory. Here, literature played an essential role in these stories and identities, keeping and spreading, shaping how we remember—Verne celebrates exploring adventure stories and discoveries that pride identity and national pride. Conversely, Wells has shown the negative side of technology, focusing on societal issues; people can think and warn about upcoming dangers. Science fiction literature is enjoyable; it remembers our past events and our love for our nationality, and warns us about the future. Good literature can show the good and bad sides of the past because people can get warnings.

Verne and Wells both wanted to use technology, but they warned society through their works, while praising it. As we know, Verne's stories are optimistic because most of his stories end with the help of technology; his characters find the solution. But not only does he show the positive side, but in his stories like *The Begum Fortune* and *Paris in the 20th century*, in his novel, he shows that science can harm society and lead to problems. But Wells also shows in both that some stories depicted the dark side of science and technology, some portray the positive side of technology, like *Men Like Gods*, where he depicted how we should use science and technology to create a better world and life. Their works are a mix of positive and negative uses of technology. And the technology plays as a double-edged sword, it helps create their story very exciting and interesting. This contrast between them is because of time. Verne lived in the late 19th century, during the Industrial Revolution, so people enjoyed technology. Wells lived in the early 20th century, so their differences are typical. Verne saw the positive changes through technology, and Wells saw that people were worried and exceedingly fearful about the outcome. Well's time was around the First World War.

Both authors have shown how new technology can change society. However, both have shown in a different way that their writings encourage the readers to think carefully about the role of technology in

the modern world. Besides technology, progress also plays a double-edged role in society. Technology is not only for discovering new things; it can create growth and exploration, and destroy and divide society. When technology is good, it's excellent, but when it's bad, it's awful. By analyzing Verne's optimism and Wells' pessimism, we better understand how progress shapes society through invention and people's choices in using them.

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